

IMPACT FACTOR: 7.86

ISSN 0976 - 8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

12th Year of Open Access

Bi-Monthly Refereed and Peer-Reviewed
Open Access e-Journal

Vol. 12, Issue - 6 (December 2021)

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Reading Caste and its Shifting Mediums in India: A Contemporary Reading

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Article History: Submitted-04/11/2021, Revised-22/12/2021, Accepted-23/12/2021, Published-31/12/2021.

Abstract:

The purpose of my study is to look at the problem of caste from the point of view of shifting "mediums" of the expression of caste. The paper argues that caste has not been erased or forgotten as per the privileged worldview in India. Rather caste-based discrimination has only remodelled, reshaped itself, and persisted in modern Indian society. I intend to study the fiction and the non-fiction created from the perspective of caste menace in India. Some of these texts that are non-fictional serve as both primary and secondary texts, the other readings in my study are aimed at establishing the historical and cultural context of caste politics in India. My focus is on contemporary scholarship in the field of caste studies. The mediums of expression may change but the experience of caste-based oppression remains the same. The paradigm shifts in the mediums of Dalit expression and resistance beginning from oral to written tradition as well as to music, cinema, social media, pictorial art, and so on that ultimately leads to action and participation in public forums and vice versa against the hegemonic social structures that act as an antidote to the politics of polarisation, alienation of the masses, and xenophobia.

Keywords: Dalits, subjectivity, xenophobia, paradigm shift.

Introduction to the Caste Menace: A Persisting Phenomenon

Caste as a social category is the stigmatic experience of generations of people in India, having existential dimensions. There are various mediums that have been exercised to create an awareness of the issue of caste-based discrimination over the years. These mediums of the expression of Dalit experience are quite powerful and important but are still not part of the mainstream academia as well as media. The neo-liberal capitalist enterprise changes the modes and forms of the practices of caste discrimination but the evil practice continues. This shows that

communal economic progress or an increasing sense of nationalism which are the buzzwords on the bar of being an Indian has very little to do with preventing caste atrocities in contemporary society.

Blind faith has taken a lead in 'modern' India despite the progress that we have made as a rapidly developing nation. It was presumed that the advent of technology would reduce blind faith but in a yet modernising setup like India, this becomes very difficult because religion and other traditional values have a stronghold on the mindsets of the people. Caste-Discrimination has a religious backing. The celebration of “Purusa-Sukta” myth dictates the origin of the lingering, millennia-long Indian Caste System,

When they divided Puruṣa how many portions did they make? What do they call his mouth, his arms? What do they call his thighs and feet? The Brahman was his mouth, of both his arms was the Rājanya made. His thighs became the Vaiśya, from his feet the Śūdra was produced. (Book 10, Hymn 90, Verses 11-12).

Caste system is fixed and rigid because it is sanctioned/constituted by invoking the power and authority of sacred texts. As a result, critically and tragically, subordinated castes have been fixed from the beginning as the psychological floor beneath which all other castes cannot fall. People from the lowest place in the Hindu hierarchical order- the Dalits are a part of Hindu society, and yet apart from it. They are treated as Untouchables, segregated from mainstream thought, society and function. Scriptural authority is invoked to designate them as polluted, untouchable and evil. The idea of relative purity sanctioned in several Hindu scriptures like Manu Smriti has impacted the behaviour of the Indian masses about caste. There is a sheer lack of understanding of the other and blatant objectification of the Dalit other. The problem has only worsened by the limitation of the caste question to the issue of reservation. Thus, we must offer an altered narrative and an insider look at the problems of caste and discrimination in India. Suraj Yengde's *Caste Matters* (2019) and Kancha Illaiah's *Why I am not a Hindu* (1996) are useful to achieve the same. The poetry of the celebrated Telugu poet Varavara Rao is also important in this regard. At 80 years of age, he has been kept imprisoned vide the controversial UAPA (Unlawful Activities Prevention Act) that allows the state to arrest individuals under a non-bailable charge of attempt to public disharmony, antinationalism, or sedition. Another intellectual Prof. Anand Teltumbde was

imprisoned under the same act in connection with the Bhima Koregaon case. The study attempts to look at the meanings of nationalism that an individual belonging to the lower caste is forced to learn. Is there a way to unlearn such nationalism and redefine it?

The work of Kancha Illaiah *Why I am not a Hindu* (1996) exposes the divided nature of the Hindu society. He also talks of the immense power of forceful assimilation that Hinduism has acquired in India. The current social scenario is fraught with the ambition of global Hindutva has gotten mixed with Indian Nationalism that has transformed itself into a global Hindu nationalism. But, in this Hindu order, the Dalits come the lowest and this has not changed despite the rapid industrialisation. Suraj Yengde in his book *Caste Matters* (2019) has changed the way we think about caste. It is no more an abstract issue in the distance. Yengde's book gives a first-person narrative of the experiences of Dalit life.

One particular scene in the novel where the mother lets her untouchable son use the maalkin's 'pure' lavatory and the indignity the mother and child have to undergo after that is particularly shocking. The entire careers of people like Narendra Dabholkar and Anand Teltumbde have been dedicated to improving society by spreading a scientific outlook, awareness, and standing against blind faith.

There have been instances of violence against the Dalits and they form a part of the daily news and social media discussions which also form a part of this study. The cause of and the magnitude of shamelessness might have changed due to legal precedents but honor killings, another form of caste stratification, are a daily occurrence. The Dalit is made the scapegoat of politics and used for public show off.

Dalit Texts: Mediums and Re-Imagined Politics

The descriptive style of Suraj Yengde is emotive. He can evoke emotions of caste consciousness even in the people who have long thought of caste as fiction. The spatiotemporal descriptive ability of Yengde in suggesting caste discrimination through remarkable and yet hidden realities is what makes him one of the most expressive and yet productively angry writers of the current generation. In *Caste Matters* (2019), he describes the little room in which he stays to be the size of a Toyota minibus and a zero-watt bulb in the room, to be occupied by over five people,

two of them sick and lying on the floor. The exploitation and the shame he mentions concerning him not being able to pay the school fee speaks of the lack of social or political goodwill in India. The sense of smallness is heightened by the strange stares and patronising looks from fellow classmates. Suraj Yengde shows the spatiotemporal dimension of Dalit life. He describes the locality of the Dalit experience. He describes the open canals full of filth. It is therefore important to understand that the struggle is intimate and existential.

Graphic descriptions of dirt cleaning are shocking. Suraj Yengde reached the limelight of Harvard University from the crowds of Indian slums where he recounts he spent a life-his childhood in Toyota size minibus. It is therefore important to understand that the life of a lower caste individual is very insignificant in the narrative of the nation that has been created. The concept of the ultra-national that has developed in the name of nationalism has harmed the Dalits and the marginalised the most because they fail to fit in a jingoistic framework without entirely giving up their identity. Such assimilation is doubly harmful because it limits how the nation can be imagined. Kancha Illaiah's book talks of a different approach to the Dalit problem. In his *Why I am Not a Hindu* (1996), he explains how the Dalits have been captured by the forceful immersive power of the Hindu religion. Their rituals and customs have been lost and needed to be rediscovered in an original way to think of a truly pluralistic India. The Dalit culture that Kancha Illaiah rediscovers is emancipated, unsuppressed, and unassumed by Hindu hegemony.

Kancha Illaiah in his autobiography narrates the story of him becoming an intellectual from a shepherd boy. The very name Kancha Illaiah Shepherd is a revolt against the established order. The identity of a shepherd was considered a sin in India. These people were the lower castes who had to bear the brunt of belonging from the lowermost strata of the society. Kancha Illaiah made it clear that he had transcended the caste boundaries of India. Thus, it is very important to understand that the caste barrier takes the grip of the mind first. It is only later that the body and the physical space get controlled.

Kancha Illaiah is one of the most radical thinkers of the 21st century. He is someone who redefines the meaning of caste. He re-aligns the history of Dalit thought with the existential reality of the community. He refuses to accept any overarching metaphors and myths and develops his own teleology of Hinduism, tracing its routes in power and discrimination. He opines that the

subjugated nature of women is a trait of the Hindu society that has seeped into Dalit culture from the high castes. Thus, it is very important to do away with this acquired illness. Illaiah also awakens the Dalit population to a new line of deities. These deities are not the Hindu gods and goddesses. These deities are rooted in nature and the environment and accept the impulses of people as natural rather than savage. A Dalits life is about the micro revolts at each stage that improves his sense of being. It is this subjective communally centered approach that promises to decenter the hegemony. Kancha Illaiah imagines a nation where the Dalits have an identity. He is an excavator of caste history and politics in India. He has studied caste from a perspective that critiques the hierarchical approach of Indians about caste. In recent times India has moved towards becoming a Hindu nation. This has led to a degeneration of the collective morality of the people and an erasure of the true essence of the Dalit identity.

Poet Varavara Rao used his imagination to create poetry that instils a sense of freedom in the mind of the people. The very fact that the government tried to suppress his voice is an indicator of the fact that there was something in his writing that spoke truth to power. Jai Prakash Narain was another voice from Bihar that understood and reacted in response to the plight of the Dalits. He advocated for class struggle along the lines of caste struggle- a worldview that Ambedkar had already suggested in the context of India. For Ambedkar, class differences have fed into the caste differences and it is class that prevents the transgression of caste limits and thus impedes liberation.

The poverty of the lower castes is not a mere chance- it is done by design so that they stay perpetually unable to come out of their situation. It is thus very important that a Dalit is made aware of his marginalized position in the Hindu/Indian society. It is only after this realization that authentic steps in the direction of self and communal liberation can be taken. It is precisely this that authors like Kancha Illaiyah and Suraj Yengde are trying to achieve. There is a subtler ironical form of caste analysis offered by Omprakash Valmiki. We will now analyse his work, *Pachchis Cauka Derh Sau* (2000).

The problems of caste oppression and discrimination have a long history and are deeply rooted in the feudal social system that did not wish to give way to the democratic laws of citizen behaviors, necessary land reforms, and redistribution, etc. Omprakash Valmiki's (1950-2013) short story *Pachchis Cauka Derh Sau* (2000), a mathematical impossibility unravels the insensitive

and exploitative nature of the landlords and feuds that leads to dehumanisation of the Dalits. We meet the narrator- Sudeep in a bus as he is returning from the city to his native village. On this bus ride, he notices the conductor mistreating uneducated villagers, and the memory of his father flashes before his eyes. He compares the conductor's body and his being to a "*shuar*". This expression is a double metaphor. One, it is a historical metaphor for the backward caste. And two, Sudeep uses his own existence and his past experience as ridicule for the oppressor. This short story takes its title from a very poignant incident that reverberates throughout the narrative. The incident is where Chowdhary, the zamindar took advantage of Sudeep's father's vulnerability and illiteracy when his wife was sick and exploited him economically and emotionally throughout his life. Caste System's self-enforcing nature conquers even the most intimate level of Indians that ultimately prevents them to rebel against the upper castes and hence lasts so long.

Dalits were deprived of ownership rights to land and property, leading to the lack of access to all sources of economic mobility. The economic conditions of the Dalits have been distressing since time immemorial. Exorbitant interest rates and simple human greed (that of the brutal zamindars, ruthless moneylenders, and landlords) combine to bind Dalits hand and foot. It was almost impossible for the Dalits to come out of the vicious cycle of loans and interests because of two reasons-One, the rate of interest was too high, and two, the cunning manipulation of maths and emotions by the upper castes. In *Pachhis Chauka Derh Sau*, Sudeep's father took a loan of hundred rupees from Chowdhary for the treatment of his wife. Chowdhary exploits him by taking advantage of his illiteracy. Sudeep's father adamantly rejects that twenty-five multiplied by four is equal to One Hundred because Chowdhary had told him that he owed that much interest on a loan and Chowdhary never lies.

On a deeper level, it shows that Dalits internalise the notion that somewhere intrinsically the upper castes are more- manly than they are. Sudeep's father believes Chowdhary not only because he has a bigger house or he owns many books. Rather, his belief's basis is the internalisation of the fact that he is less of a man than the zamindar. Clearly, over time Dalits internalize the weaknesses and the discrimination and begin to believe the oppressive and unjust explanations that the Brahmanical society offers them. It is, therefore, necessary to understand that a sense of nothingness can take the form of a community feeling in a society like India which has long legitimized the ostracisation of people based on caste.

It is to be noted that the Shudras are that group of the population who comprise most of the landless laborers working on the farm. Along with the curse of untouchability, the Dalits had no right to have any property. The privileged very conveniently created a society that is hierarchically structured in a graded inequality, giving undue advantages to those belonging to the upper caste. They relegated Dalits to be silent occupants of the liminal space to which they have been confined for centuries. An upward movement in the caste hierarchy is not permitted. It is perhaps this reason that B.R. Ambedkar called for the destruction of Hinduism as there is no possibility of an egalitarian treatment of all strata of people of the society. Omprakash Valmiki's short story *Pachhis Chauka Derh Sau* was written in the year 2000 making it clear that it is independent India that is being depicted. But we see independence and democracy both failing when we find this poor Dalit family. Sudeep's father, throughout the narrative, is depicted in a sorry and frightened state, grovelling, bending head, and begging with folded hands for anything and everything to Master Phool Singh, Master Shivnarayan, and Chowdhary- the people belonging to the upper caste.

Pitaji ki khushi mein bhi girgirahat jhalak rhi thi.

Food, water, shelter, and clothing are some of the basic needs for human survival, and these are systematically denied to the Dalits. Every page, in fact every line of *Pachhis Chauka Derh Sau* is filled with immediate and moving details about the lower caste people and their lives. The scene where the clothes of the father and the little boy are mentioned deserves a comment. The father-son duo is wearing tattered, dirty, and faded rags showing how society and the political will have failed them. The father-son-teacher triad shows a unique conflict in the story. The father is a staunch believer in the caste system and he naively believes that *pacchis chauke dedh sau* comes from Chowdhary- the zamindar and is thus a better truth than what is written in the book. The student-son gets confused as to who of his two ideals- the father or the teacher are misleading him. On a deeper level, it is the internalisation of the caste hierarchy that has led to the increasing differences and exploitation and that passing easy with the society at large.

Access to education is central to the achievement of interrelated human rights outcomes without which India cannot holistically progress. Dalits have experienced consistent denial of education since forever. And when allowed, they frequently are segregated from other students,

humiliated, and abused in front of their peers. Teachers are reported more to this than non-marginalized students with details of slurs, put-downs, discouragement, and abuse related to their religion, culture, and caste. This systematic power abuse has long-term effects on student outcomes. I intend to point out a scene from *Pachchis Chauka Derh Sau* where Sudeep tries to 'assert' that his father has rightly said that twenty-five multiplied by four is equal to One Hundred and Fifty. The behaviour of the teacher with the child is completely unacceptable. One can understand that mistakes call for a scolding in a student's life but a swift shift to caste markers and simultaneous hurling of abuses is completely unacceptable. It indicates the unbecoming of any teacher. Sudeep faces extreme hostility in front of the entire class because he tried to assert his view was contradictory to him. Sudeep is forced to be humiliated as a punishment only because he is born in a Dalit community. And, Dalits are supposed to accept every word coming out of the mouth of an upper-caste without questioning it. On the other hand, the father of this child is beguiled by the hollow mannerisms of the zamindar Chowdhary and sees worldly wisdom as different from real wisdom. He is illiterate and he accepts that saying, '*mere liye to kaala akshar bhains barabar hai.*' Still, he knows that *pachchis chauka derh sau* because it is said by a man (that is, Chowdhary) who is higher than any teacher and any book. And this is the only time when we see Sudeep's father confident and assertive. Ironically, this attitude is to defend an upper-caste man. This is nothing but the scared faith on the oppressive higher castes and their oppressive mechanisms, especially their own internalized sense of being less worthy than people with higher social standing.

The problem of caste and exploitation is way deeper than caste hierarchy- nevertheless, the menace began as Ambedkar rightly pointed out with the Brahmanization of Hinduism. More importantly, knowledge/ education comes up as the differentiator here reinforcing Ambedkar's ideas about Dalit education. A peculiar kind of meaninglessness that arises out of loss of control over one's life is seen in the lives of these Dalits. There is no denying that untouchability was abolished in India and there are laws to protect the rights of the Shudras and the Ati-Shudras. The question however is how many of these laws can safeguard the dignity of the lower castes in daily social life. This is how both non-fictional and creative works strive to make the Dalits a heard, respected part of the mainstream thereby achieving the truest nationalistic goals.

Caste in India transcends religion and culture. Caste has become a social division category

by itself, and therefore we need to have, a sort of, a “biased” look on it. Biased in the sense that a loud and provocative look where we do not provide an alternate discourse because the minute we do that, we allow the same trope of modernity, urbanity, and industrial development to be used time and again. There cannot be an ideological alternative for an existential problem. Any alternate narrative would just be an excuse to brush the problem under the carpet. Dalit discourse is invisibilized in many ways, and if I include other approaches it will fall in the same pattern later it will be subsumed under the ‘mainstream’ texts.

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